

THERMALLY ACTIVATED MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES

D. Bollas^{a, b}, P. Pappas^{a, c}, J. Parthenios^{b, c}, G. Trakakis^{a, c} and C. Galiotis^{a, b, c}

^a Department of Materials Science, University of Patras, Patras 26504, Greece

^b Institute of Chemical Engineering and High Temperature Chemical Processes, Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH), P.O. BOX 1414, Patras 265 04, Greece

^c Inter-Departmental Graduate Studies Programme in “Polymer Science and Technology, University of Patras, Greece

Corresponding author: e-mail: c.galiotis@iceht.forth.gr, galiotis@upatras.gr

SUMMARY

Thermally activated multifunctional composite materials which have the ability of shape change have developed by two different ideas. The first way is by incorporating actuators such as Shape Memory Alloy wires. The integration of prestrained SMA wires with small diameters inside the material leads to a variation of composite material's properties, such as stiffness, damping capacity and shape in response to an external or an internal stimulus. The second way is by taking advantage of the thermal and mechanical anisotropy of high performance fibrous composites. A selective thermal activation of one or more layers inside the material would create thermal stresses, which could induce shape change to the material at the macroscopic level.

Keywords: Deformation, shape memory alloys, stress, thermal expansion, anisotropy

ABSTRACT

The selection of materials for a given engineering application is normally based upon their overall physicommechanical behaviour under static, dynamic and occasional harsh environmental conditions. By combining two or more materials together a much more broader range of properties can be obtained. Nowadays there is a vast population of monolithic or composite materials for the designer to choose from and extensive property-specific tables are available. In many cases, however, an engineering material is required to perform a multitude of functions and this poses an extra difficulty to the selection process. Already, a great deal of research effort is directed in the development of materials that can be classified as “adaptive” or “intelligent”. These are materials or material systems certain properties of which, such as stiffness, damping capacity or even shape, may be varied in response to an external or internal stimulus.

Fibre-reinforced polymeric materials exhibit high intrinsic strength/stiffness per unit weight and excellent fatigue behaviour even in corrosive environments. In addition the current vast choice of constituent materials but also of fibre architecture (e.g. unidirectional tape, 2D and 3D fabrics, etc.) can lead to materials with tailored properties in any given direction. Thus, polymer composites are particularly attractive as candidates for the production of adaptive materials for a number of applications.

One special class of adaptive composites is those that incorporate thin shape memory alloys (SMA) in the form of wires, strips or films. SMA materials such as binary NiTi or ternary NiTiX (where X could be Cu, Co, Fe, Nb etc) have the ability to recover their own original shape after a cycle, which includes cooling-deforming-heating with the simultaneous generation of mechanical work, a function related to a reversible

transformation between different crystal structures, called austenite and martensite. Under constrained conditions, pre-strained SMA wires are prevented from regaining their original shape and thus high recovery stresses are generated. Henceforth, SMA materials are able to sense thermal, mechanical or electrical stimuli and, in response, to activate the host medium in a controllable fashion.

In this work, the ability of single SMA wires to act as internal stress generators in fibrous polymer composite systems has been investigated. The stress fields recorded both at the specimen level and internally in the reinforcing fibers by means of Raman microscopy measurements have confirmed that SMA wires can serve as effective stress-actuators. The efficiency of stress generation depends on the wire alloy composition and level of prestrain prior to incorporation into the composite medium. The internal stress distribution in the composite fibers decayed from a position just above the wire surface to the edges of the specimen reaching zero at a distance of approximately 3000 μm . The maximum value of stress recorded in the fibers at a distance of approximately one wire radius was 227 MPa. The significance of these results in the design and operation of adaptive composites systems similar to those examined here is discussed.

Also, another possibility for the development of a multifunctional composite without inserting actuators has been examined. An idea that has gained ground recently is to exploit the thermal anisotropy of a composite laminate in order to induce shape changes by internal heating. Indeed a selective thermal activation of one or more layers inside the material would create thermal stresses, which could induce shape change to the material at the macroscopic level, just as those observed in the bimetallic strips. In the classical composite laminate case, each lamina can have a different Young modulus and a different thermal expansion coefficient. When the temperature is increased due to the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients each lamina will elongate to a different extent and if the bonding is perfect, the structure will have to bend. Thus one can design composite laminates that undergo controlled bending by either internal (or external) heating without adding or integrating actuators or other devices.

In this work we have developed and tested a new method for controlling shape changes in composites by means of heating up the reinforcing fibres of the composite. The proposed method represents a significant improvement because in most high performance applications for which multifunctionality is required, carbon fibres are the main reinforcing agents and therefore there is no need to add a bundle of dry fibres or a metal plate to heat up the composite. As shown here individual carbon fibres can be pulled out from the edges of constituent fabrics prior to lamination so as to fabricate the necessary electrical connections for current flow on the completion of autoclave lamination procedure. The resulting shape change was determined and the stresses generated during heating were measured via a 3-point bending device. The possibility of using the reinforcing fibres of a multi-directional composite as activators for inducing specific deformation modes is discussed.

References

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